

ISSN No. : XXXX-XXXX
Volume : 01
Issue : 01
DOI :

Publisher
**ROGANIDAN VIKRUTIVIGYAN PG ASSOCIATION
FOR PATHOLOGY AND RADIOGNOSIS**
Reg. No. : MAHA-703/16(NAG) Year of Establishment – 2016

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF DIAGNOSTICS AND RESEARCH

Comparative study of Trayodashng Guggulu with Vishgarbh Tail and Vishtinduk Vati with Vishgarbh Tail in the management of Katishoola.

Dr.Vinita Tyagi¹

¹Professor/HoD, Shalya Tantra Department,
Skd Government Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Muzaffarnagar, Uttar Pradesh.

Corresponding author: Dr. Vinita Tyagi

Article Info: Published on: 02 /01/2024

Cite this article as: - Dr. Vinita Tyagi

Abstract

The most frequent clinical symptom of spinal pathology in musculoskeletal illnesses i.e., low back pain (*Katishoola*). In developing nations, lifestyle changes have harmed biological systems. The development of spinal illnesses is largely influenced by poor sleeping positions, sports activities, rapid movement during travel, and improper sitting postures. Being the most delicate musculoskeletal system and supporting the full weight of a human, the spine, especially the lumbar spine, is where this condition is most frequently observed. It is said that the *kati pradesha* (lumber region) is a significant *Vata dosha* seat. *Vata* is vitiated in the swasthana of *Katishoola*. The signs of the disease can be seen in a variety of diseases, including *Katishoola*, *Trikshoola*, *Prishtashoola*, and *Vatik shoola*, even though the ancient Acharyas did not name a single illness as *Katishoola*. *Katishoola* is mentioned by all the Acharyas under *Vatavyadhi*. In this study, a total of 50 clinically diagnosed patients with *Katishoola* were divided into two equal groups. Patients in group A were treated with *Tryodashanaga Guggulu* and *Vishgarbh Tail* and the patients in group B were treated with *Vishtinduk Vati* and *Vishgarbh Tail*. Seven different parameters like *Ruk* (pain), *Stamba* (Morning stiffness), *Shopha* (swelling), *Sparsha Asahatva* (tenderness), Restricted movement, *Dehasyapi Pravakrta* (scoliosis,) and S.L.R test were analyzed for 6 visits during 3 months of the treatment. In this study, we found that *Tryodashanaga Guggulu* and *Vishgarbh Tail* are more effective in managing *katishoola* than *Vishtinduk Vati* and *vishgarbh tail*.

Keywords: *katishoola*, *Vishgarbh Tail*, *Vishtinduk Vati*

Introduction:

According to Ayurveda, *Kati Pradesha* is where the vitiated *Vata* localizes, which leads to the emergence of *Katishoola* as a clinical condition ^[1]. *Kaphavrita Vyana Vayu* blocks the flow of *Rasa*, and *Rakta Dhatu* during pathogenesis, limiting the emergence of succeeding *Dhatus* like *Mamsa*, *Meda*, *Asthi*, and so forth, leading to gradual structural or functional changes in *Kati Pradesha* ^[2]. Later, signs like *Shoola*, *Shopha*, and *Stambha* appear. The two primary therapeutic techniques employed in Ayurveda are *shodhan chikitsa* and *shaman chikitsa* ^[3]. There are explanations for *Snehana*, *Upanaha*, *Agni Karma*, *Raktamokshana*, and other *Shodhan chikitsa* instruments. The *Shaman chikitsa* formulas known as *Kwath*, *Vati*, *Guggulu*, *Taila*, *Ghrita*, and others are discussed already. Currently, *Katishoola* (low back pain) is a quickly expanding bush of suffering ^[1]. For lumbar spondylosis patients wishing to improve their quality of life, frequent conservative treatments include analgesics, anti-inflammatory drugs, steroid injections, and physical therapy ^[4]. The only treatment options for severe lumbar spondylosis are surgical procedures like spinal fusion and spinal decompression ^[5]. However, these operations do not satisfy patients' expectations due to their high cost and therapeutic limitations. Patients are frequently forced to take analgesics for a prolonged amount of time following surgery. In Ayurveda, pharmacological and effect-oriented treatments like *Trayodashang Guggulu* with *Vish garbh tel sanehan* are recommended for diseases with similar clinical scenarios ^[6]. *Vishtindukadi vati* is Ayurvedic drug mentioned in *Ras tantra sara* and *sidha prayoga samgraha*. The main content of *vishtindukadi vati* is the *kuchla*, along with *maricha*, *chinha phala*, and *pugaphala*, indicated in opium addiction. The main content of *vishtindukadi vati* is *Kupilu* which has properties like *vata-shamak*, *chitta-avasadahar* (antidepressant properties), and *hridya daurbalyahar* (cardiac tonic). Comparison studies of “*Trayodashang Guggulu* and *Vishgarbh Tail*” with “*Vishtinduk Vati* and *Vishgarbh Tail*” will pave the way to understanding the efficacy of both medicines in the management of “*Katishoola*”.

Review of literature:

Worldwide, low back pain is a relatively prevalent health issue and a key contributor to disability, impacting both work performance and overall well-being ^[7]. According to the 2010 Global Burden of Disease Study, low back pain is one of the top 10 illnesses and accidents that cause the most DALYs globally ^[8]. Children and adolescents have a lower prevalence rate than adults, but it is increasing. Between the ages of 35 and 55, prevalence rises and peaks. In many parts of the world, low back pain is the most common reason for activity restriction and work absence, placing a significant financial burden on individuals, families, communities, businesses, and governments ^[9]. With more than 100 million lost workdays annually, low back pain was shown to be the most prevalent cause of disability in young adults in the United Kingdom ^[10]. Low back pain is thought to generate 149 million lost workdays in the US annually, with associated expenses estimated to range from \$100 to \$200 billion ^[11]. The most common work-related musculoskeletal condition affecting IT professionals in India is low back pain ^[12]. The causes of 37% of low back pain reported globally were determined to be work-related risk factors ^[13, 14, 15, 16, 17]. The percentage varied slightly by location (21% - 41%) and was greater in places with a generally lower level of health. The ancient science of life known as "Ayurveda" has endured the test of time in a magnificent way. According to numerous modern scientific parameters, the manuscripts/scriptures that are thought to have been authored 5000 years ago contain medicines and treatment techniques that are still effective today. The "*Tridosha*" and "*Panchamahabhoot*" *Siddhanta*, which are eternal, are what keeps our field of medicine alive ^[18].

One of the *Tridoshas*, together with *Pitta* and *Kapha*, *Vata* has a variety of diseases that can affect any part of the body. Pain, or *Shula* in Sanskrit, is the primary sign of *Vata* vitiation. In "*Vatadrite Rujah Nasti*" The most frequent

symptom for which a person seeks medical help is this pain, which is well-recognized as a sign of the condition [19]. 80 *Vataja Nanatmaja Vyadhi* are mentioned by almost all of the Ayurvedic Acharyas [20]. A *Vataja Nanatmaja Vyadhi* named *Katigraha* is mentioned by Sharangadhara. He described it as "*Katisthambhana Vedana Vishesha*," an illness characterized by stiffness and pain in the *Kati pradesha* (Pelvic region) [6]. Acharya Sodhala defines *katigraha* as a situation typified by vitiated *vata*, either *shuddha* or with *Ama*, taking ashraaya in the *Katipradesha* causing *Ruja* and *Graham* in the area [21].

The Shodhala explains the *Samprapti, Lakshana* of *Kati Graha* in the *Kayachikitsa Khanda, Vataroga Adhikara*. He has provided descriptions of numerous *Kati Shoola* formulas and has especially mentioned *Trayodashanga Guggulu* for *Kati Graha* [22]. According to research, the frequency of LBP in the Indian population ranges from 6.2% (in the general population) to 92% (among construction workers). Low back pain is the most common reason for impairment in patients under the age of forty-five and the third most common reason for disability in people beyond the age of forty-five [23]. It can have severe medical and financial effects. Although it can be tremendously disabling, this issue, which allegedly has a favorable natural history, has presented a challenge to healthcare professionals.

No direct reference is made to *Kati Shoola* as a distinct illness in any of the Brihatrayees. Acharya Charaka didn't specifically refer to the disease, but by quoting "*Hetu Sthaana Visheshat Ca Bhavet Roga Vishesha Krit*," he implied that all conditions that can result from *Vata* localization in particular bodily parts were included. There is a smattering of different *Sandhi, Snaayu*, and *Peshi* in the *Kati* area. A site called *Sandhi* is where two or more structures come together. *Sandhi* is seen as an organ rather than a single structure [24].

There are various structures, which contribute to preserving the stability of the joint. Ligaments, also

known as *snaayu*, are those structures that aid in the appropriate binding of the joint. They connect the bones, aid in directing action, and help to stop unneeded and excessive motion. The tone in the muscles aids in keeping the joint in proper alignment. In the joints, *Shleshmadharakala*, which is supported by *Shleshaka Kapha*, aids in lubrication, supplies nutrients and keeps the joint firmly fused. Therefore, the vitiation of *Vata* can result in these structures' diseases in *Kati Pradesha*, which will hinder their ability to operate [25].

Objectives :

Comparison between the efficacy of "*Trayodashang Guggulu* and *Vishgarbh Tail*" with "*Vishtinduk Vati* and *Vishgarbh Tail*" in the management of "*Katishoola*"

Methods:

It was an open-label, randomized clinical trial. A total of 50 patients (25 patients in each group) were randomly divided into two groups by computer-generated randomization. The study was approved by the Institutional Ethical Committee (IEC).

Inclusion criteria:

Patients of either gender, having age between 18 and 70 years, willing to participate in the trial, with clinical signs and symptoms of *Katishoola*, having chronicity of disease <5 years. Patients with traumatic vertebral disorder without paralysis or radiating pain (only local pain) History of Lumbosacral sprain /strain/Lumbago for more than two months. Lumbar Disc disease without herniation of nucleus pulposus Arthritis of the lower spine.

Exclusion criteria:

Patients having a history of recent spinal surgery or implanted instrumentation, long-term intake of steroid and cytotoxic treatment, comorbidities like uncontrollable hypertension, diabetes mellitus,

etc., evidence of malignancy, participation in any clinical trial within the last 6 months, and pregnant or lactating women were excluded from the study. Patients with traumatic vertebral disorders (suffering from paralysis) Infection of the spine especially Tuberculosis, Brucellosis and Pyogenic osteomyelitis, etc., Neoplasm of the spine referred to low backache from pelvic, abdomen or diseases of the thorax.

Grouping :

Group A: *Tryodashanaga Guggulu*, two tablets (500 mg. each) twice a day after lunch and dinner with lukewarm water with *abhyangam* with *Vishgarbh Tail* once a day in the morning for 90 days.

Group B: *Vishtinduk Vati*, one tablet (30 mg. each) twice a day after lunch and dinner with lukewarm water with *abhyangam* with *Vishgarbh Tail* once a day in the morning for 90 days.

Trial drugs :

1. *Trayodashang Guggulu*
2. *Vishtinduk Vati*
3. *Vishgarbh Tail*

Criteria for assessment:

The improvement will be assessed mainly based on relief in the clinical signs and symptoms of the disease. To assess the effect of treatment and therapy procedure objectively, all the signs and symptoms were given numbers for scoring depending upon their severity which is as below:

Assessment:

The assessment was done based on changes in nonparametric variables.

Nonparametric variable: - All registered patients of “*Katishoola*” were assessed based on certain symptoms such as pain, stiffness, swelling, tenderness, and Straight Leg Raise (SLR).

Si.No.	Assessment criteria	Intensity
1	Pain(Ruka)	
	No pain	0
	Mild pain but no difficulty in walking	1
	Moderate pain and mild difficulty in walking	2
	Severe pain with severe difficulty in walking	3
2	Stambha (Morning stiffness)	
	No Stambha	0
	Mild	1
	Moderate	2
	Severe	3
3	Swelling(Shopha)	
	No Shopha	0
	Mild	1
	Moderate	2
	Severe	3
4	Tenderness(Sparsha asahatava)	
	No Tenderness	0
	Mild	1
	Moderate	2
	Severe	3
5	Restricted Movement	
	No Restricted movement	0
	Mild	1
	Moderate	2
	Severe	3
6	Dehasyapi Pravakrata (Scoliosis)	
	Absent	0
	Mild	1
	Moderate	2
	Severe	3
7	S.L.R. Test	
	Straight leg raising 90 – 76	0
	Straight leg raising 75 – 61	1
	Straight leg raising 60– 46	2
	Straight leg raising 45 – 31	3

Observations and results :

By analysis of data, it was observed that the maximum number of patients were between 20 and 60 years of age group. Demographic observations related to *Nidana* – a maximum of the total patients were suffering from the disease for 1–2 years. All patients (100%) presented with the symptom of pain and 24 patients in both groups were presented with restricted SLR, followed by patients suffering from stiffness. Some were presented with tenderness and swelling. In both groups, only two patients have *Dehasyapi Pravakrata* (scoliosis).

Among 25 patients treated with *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* 18 were female patients and 7 were male patients of which 10 were in the age group of 20-40 years, 14 were between 40-60 years, and 1 above 60 years. 15 patients were

following a vegetarian diet while 3 were Non-vegetarian diet followers. During the first visit, 4 patients suffered from severe pain, 18 from moderate pain, and 3 from mild pain. Morning stiffness was severe for 1 patient, moderate for 16 patients, mild for 4 patients, and 4 were not experiencing morning stiffness. One patient was suffering from severe swelling, 8 with moderate swelling, 6 with mild swelling, and 10 without swelling. *Sparsha Asahatva* (tenderness) was severe for 2 patients, moderate for 16 patients, mild for 6 patients, and no tenderness for 1 patient. There was no one with severe restricted movement but 12 patients were suffering with moderate restricted movement, 9 patients with mild restricted movement, and 4 patients without restricted movement. There was only one patient with both mild and moderate scoliosis. Thirteen patients showed severe issues during the S.L.R test, 7 patients with moderate issues, 4 patients with mild issues, and 1 patient without any issues.

Among 25 patients treated with *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha* 18 were female patients and 7 were male patients of which 17 were in the age group of 20-40 years, 7 were between 40-60 years, and 1 was above 60 years. 16 patients were following a vegetarian diet while 4 were Non-vegetarian diet followers. During the first visit, 3 patients suffered from severe pain, 19 from moderate pain, and 3 from mild pain. Morning stiffness was severe for 1 patient, moderate for 18 patients, mild for 5 patients and 1 was not experiencing morning stiffness. No patients were suffering from severe swelling, 9 with moderate swelling, 6 with mild swelling, and 10 without swelling. *Sparsha Asahatva* (tenderness) was severe for 1 patient, moderate for 18 patients, mild for 5 patients, and no tenderness for 2 patients. There was no one with severe restricted movement but 14 patients were suffering with moderate restricted movement, 11 patients with mild restricted movement, and 1 patient without restricted movement. There was only one patient with mild scoliosis. Nine patients showed severe issues during the S.L.R test, 11 patients with moderate issues, 4 patients with mild issues, and 1 patient without any issues.

Fig.1 Ruk (pain) for visits 1-6 during the treatment using *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* and *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila*

During Ruk (pain) (Fig.1) assessment for the treatment using *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* and *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila*, for *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* from visit 4, there is a reduction in pain for patients compared to the patients treated with *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila*. In visit 5, there is a drastic reduction in pain followed by a total reduction of pain in the 6th visit for *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* whereas in *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila* in visits 5 and 6 there are patients with pain. According to One-Way ANOVA, the f-ratio value for *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* is 47.50633. The p-value is < .00001. The result is significant at $p < .05$ and *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila* the f-ratio value is 23.79813. The p-value is < .00001. The result is significant at $p < .05$.

Fig.2 Stamba (Morning stiffness) for visits 1-6 during the treatment using *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* and *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila*

In *stamba* (Morning stiffness) (Fig.2) for *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* from visit 3, there is a reduction in morning stiffness for patients compared to the patients treated with *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila*. From visit 4, there is a drastic reduction in morning stiffness followed by a total reduction of pain in the 6th visit for *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* whereas in *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila* there are patients with morning stiffness till visit 6. According to One-Way ANOVA, the f-ratio value for *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* is 26.21691. The p-value is < .00001. The result is significant at $p < .05$ and *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila* the f-ratio value is 30.47904. The p-value is < .00001. The result is significant at $p < .05$

Fig.3 Shopha (swelling) for visit 1-6 during the treatment using *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* and *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila*

For *Shopha* (swelling) (Fig.3) patients treated with *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila* show more swelling than *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila*. From visit 4, there is a reduction in swelling for patients treated with both medicines. From visit 5, there is a reduction in swelling for *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* and *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila*. According to One-Way ANOVA, the f-ratio value for

Trayodasang Guggulu with *Vishgarbha Taila* is 8.15299. The p-value is < .00001. The result is significant at $p < .05$ and *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila* the f-ratio value is 8.25301. The p-value is < .00001. The result is significant at $p < .05$.

Fig.4 Sparsha Asahatva (tenderness) for visits 1-6 during the treatment using *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* and *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila*

Sparsha Asahatva (tenderness) (Fig.4) for the treatment by *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* from visit 3, there is a reduction in tenderness for patients compared to the patients treated with *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila*. In visits 5 and 6, the tenderness is reduced in *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha* than in *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila*. According to One-Way ANOVA, the f-ratio value for *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* is 31.91362. The p-value is < .00001. The result is significant at $p < .05$ and *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila* the f-ratio value is 23.47406. The p-value is < .00001. The result is significant at $p < .05$.

Fig.5 Restricted movement for visits 1-6 during the treatment using *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* and *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila*

Restricted movement (Fig.5) assessment for *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* from visit 3, there is a reduction in restricted movement issues for patients compared to the patients treated with *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila*. In visit 5 only 2 patients shows restricted movement at a mild level for *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* whereas in *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila*, there are 5 patients. According to One-Way ANOVA, the f-ratio value for *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* is 21.28205. The p-value is < .00001. The result is significant at $p < .05$ and *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila* the f-ratio value is 19.19761. The p-value is < .00001. The result is significant at $p < .05$.

Fig.6 *Dehasyapi Pravakrata* (scoliosis) for visits 1-6 during the treatment using *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* and *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila*

In *Dehasyapi Pravakrata* (scoliosis) (Fig.6) from visit 1 itself the patients with scoliosis are very less in both cases. From visit 2, there are no notable changes in the scoliosis for both medicines. According to One-Way ANOVA, the f-ratio value for *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* is 0.41026. The p-value is .800968. The result is not

significant at $p < .05$ and *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila* the f-ratio value is 0.75. The p-value is .559894. The result is not significant at $p < .05$.

Fig.7 S.L.R test for visits 1-6 during the treatment using *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* and *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila*

Straight leg raising (Fig.7) test for treatment by *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* there were 12 patients with level 3 S.L.R issues. Only 1 patient has a level 3 problem on the second visit. In visit 4 there is only 2 patients with S.L.R issue and in the 6th visit, S.L.R is completely reduced. There are 9 among 25 patients treated with *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila* who have extreme S.L.R issues during visit 1, for 3 among them the issues continue in visit 2 and 1 patient suffered the level 3 problem in visit 3 also. In visit 5 there are patients with level 2 and level 1 SLR issues and 9 patient shows level 1 issue in visit 6. According to One-Way ANOVA, the f-ratio value for *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* is 41.83953. The p-value is < .00001. The result is significant at $p < .05$ and *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila* the f-ratio value is 22.57732. The p-value is < .00001. The result is significant at $p < .05$.

Fig.8 Group A

Si.No.	Criteria	n	Mean		d	Relief (%)	SD(+/-)	SE(+/-)	t	p
			BT	AT						
1	Ruk (pain)	25	2.04	0.12	1.92	94.11765	0.54	0.1527	13.3565	<0.05
2	Stamba (Morning stiffness)	21	1.86	0.05	1.81	97.31183	0.2	0.0617	29.3254	<0.05
3	Shopha (swelling)	15	1.67	0.07	1.6	95.80838	0.2	0.073	21.9089	<0.05
4	Sparsha Asahatva (tenderness)	24	1.83	0.04	1.79	97.81421	0.2	0.0577	31.0037	<0.05
5	Restricted movement	21	1.57	0.05	1.52	96.81529	0.2	0.0617	24.6268	<0.05
6	Dehasyapi Pravakrata (scoliosis)	2	1.5	0.5	1	66.66667	0.2	0.2	5	<0.05
7	S.L.R test	24	2.375	0.08	2.295	96.63158	0.89	0.2569	9.2441	<0.05

The t-test value for *Trayodasang Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* except for *Ruk* (pain) and S.L.R test is < .05. The rest of the results are significant at $p < .05$. Except *Dehasyapi pravakrata* (scoliosis) other six parameters show significant relief (95.8% - 97.81%).

Fig.9 Group B

Si.No.	Criteria	n	Mean		d	Relief (%)	SD(+/-)	SE(+/-)	t	p
			BT	AT						
1	Ruk (pain)	25	2	0.56	1.44	72	0.506623	0.1433	10.0492	<0.05
2	Stamba (Morning stiffness)	24	1.83	0.28	1.55	84.69945	0.458258	0.1323	11.7169	<0.05
3	Shopha (swelling)	15	1.53	0.12	1.41	92.15686	0.331662	0.1211	11.6427	<0.05
4	Sparsha Asahatva (tenderness)	24	1.79	0.28	1.51	84.35754	0.458258	0.1323	0.1323	<0.05
5	Restricted movement	24	1.54	0.2	1.34	87.01299	0.408248	0.1179	11.3703	<0.05
6	Dehasyapi Pravakrata (scoliosis)	1	1	0	1	100	0	0	0	<0.05
7	S.L.R test	24	2.2	0.36	1.84	83.63636	0.489898	0.1414	13.0108	<0.05

The t-test value for *Vishtinduk vati* with *Vishgarbha Taila* only *Ruk* (pain) and S.L.R test are <.05. The result is significant at $p < .05$. All the parameters show relief at the final visit than the first visit (72% - 100%).

Fig.10 Comparison between group A and Group B

Si.No.	Criteria	Mean Score					
		Trayodasang Guggulu			Vishtinduk vati		
		BT	AT	Relief (%)	BT	AT	Relief (%)
1	Ruk (pain)	2.04	0.12	94.117647	2	0.56	72
2	Stamba (Morning stiffness)	1.86	0.05	97.311828	1.83	0.28	84.69945
3	Shopha (swelling)	1.67	0.07	95.808383	1.53	0.12	92.15686
4	Sparsha Asahatva (tenderness)	1.83	0.04	97.814208	1.79	0.28	84.35754
5	Restricted movement	1.57	0.05	96.815287	1.54	0.2	87.01299
6	Dehasyapi Pravakrata (scoliosis)	1.5	0.5	66.666667	1	0	100
7	S.L.R test	2.375	0.08	96.631579	2.2	0.36	83.63636

According to the comparison study, the patients in Group A, treated with *Tryodashang guggulu* show significant relief in the health conditions which are assessed in this study. The pain relief is 94.117647% in Group A while in Group B it is 72%, the relief to *stamba* is 97.311% in Group A but in Group B it is 84.69945%. Restricted movement shows 96.81% relief in Group A in which Group B it is 87.01299%. In S.L.R test Group A have 96.631579% relief and the relief percentage in Group B is 83.63636%.

Discussion :

Pain intensity, morning stiffness, swelling, tenderness, restricted movement, and S.L.R test during the treatment with both medicines were compared, which showed the patients treated with *Trayodashanga Guggulu* with *Vishgarbha Taila* is better than *Vishtindukadi vati* with *Vishgarbha Tail*. Many people suffer from the joint condition *katishoola*. Provocation of the *Vata Dosha* has a major effect on *Sandhi* in this illness. To sustain a *Sandhi's* range of motion, the *Vyana Vayu* is an essential functional component. The roles of *Shleshaka Kapha* and *Sleshmadhara Kala* are influenced by the annulus fibrosus and nucleus pulposus, which serve as a cushion and promote healthy spinal joint function. The majority of *Trayodashang Guggulu's* contents are *Ushna* and *Vata-Kapha Doshahara* in nature because 71.42 percent of the drug constituents have *Tikta rasa*, 57.14 percent have *Katu rasa*, 57.14 percent have *Laghu guna*, and 42.85 percent have *Ruksha guna*. 71.42 percent of pharmaceuticals have *Ushna Virya*, while 57.14 percent of medications contain *Vata-Kapha Hara*. The *Vata-Kapha hara* components of *Trayodashang Guggulu*, as previously mentioned, help to alleviate *Katishoola*, a condition that is brought on by the vitiation of the *Vata* and *Kapha doshas*. *Shashtra* claims that *Guggulu* is a *Vatamedo hara* and that it is more potent at calming *Vata* and reducing *Katishoola* when taken with *Ghrita*. *Vishgarbh Tail* is referred to as *Shoolahara* and *Vata shamana* in numerous places in *Shashtra*. Thus, it is discovered that *guggulu* is more successful at calming *katishoola* when used in conjunction with *Vishgarbh Tail Trayodashang*.

Conclusion :

When managing *Katishool*, *Tryodashanaga Guggulu* and *Vishgarbh Tail* perform better than *Vishtinduk Vati* and *Vishgarbh Tail*. With the addition of *Vishgarbha Tail abhyangam*, the already well-known *Trayodashang Guggulu*, particularly for *Katishoola*, has even more potent effects due to the extra *shoolhara* qualities of *Vishgarbha Tail*. Both *Trayodashang Guggulu* and *Vishgarbh Tail* are mostly suggested for *Katishoola*; hence, in this case, when the patient

was experiencing lower back discomfort, the application of this medicine combination provided effective alleviation.

Reference :

1. Ediriweera ER, Gunathilka HD, Weerasinghe KD, Kalawana OT. Efficacy of traditional treatment regimen on Kati Shoola with special reference to lumbar spondylolisthesis. *Ayu*. 2013 Jan;34(1):86-9. doi 10.4103/0974-8520.115435. PMID: 24049411; PMCID: PMC3764887.
2. Moharana P, Roushan R. A critical review of Vyana Vayu in modern Physiological Perspective. *International journal of basic and applied research*. 2018;8(11):75-82.
3. Kavya G, Sharma S. Panchakarma Chikitsa in Stree Roga. *Int J Res Rev*. 2016 Aug;3(8):4-5.
4. Prasath RA, Prashanth D, Parthasarathy K, Varghese M, Palani P, Kayarohanam S, Janakiraman AK, Sriram N. Lumbar Spondylosis: Clinical Presentation And Treatment Approaches—A Systematic Review. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*. 2022 Dec 31:10384-91.
5. Samuel AM, Moore HG, Cunningham ME. Treatment for degenerative lumbar spondylolisthesis: current concepts and new evidence. *Current reviews in musculoskeletal medicine*. 2017 Dec;10:521-9.
6. Gupta N, Choudhary K, Mangal G. Katigraha (Lumbar Spondylosis) managed by Katidhara and Basti: A Case report. *International Journal of Ayurveda and Traditional Medicine*. 2020 Jun 8;2(2):10-4.
7. Wu A, March L, Zheng X, Huang J, Wang X, Zhao J, Blyth FM, Smith E, Buchbinder R, Hoy D. Global low back pain prevalence and years lived with disability from 1990 to 2017: estimates from the Global Burden of Disease Study 2017. *Annals of translational medicine*. 2020 Mar;8(6).
8. Hoy D, March L, Brooks P, Blyth F, Woolf A, Bain C, Williams G, Smith E, Vos T, Barendregt J, Murray C. The global burden of low back pain: estimates from the Global Burden of Disease 2010 study. *Annals of the rheumatic diseases*. 2014 Jun 1;73(6):96874.
9. Ganesan S, Acharya AS, Chauhan R, Acharya S. Prevalence and risk factors for low back pain in 1,355 young adults: a cross-sectional study. *Asian spine journal*. 2017 Aug;11(4):610.
10. Awosan KJ, Yikawe SS, Oche OM, Oboirien M. Prevalence, perception and correlates of low back pain among healthcare workers in tertiary health institutions in Sokoto, Nigeria. *Ghana medical journal*. 2017;51(4):164-74.
11. Freburger JK, Holmes GM, Agans RP, Jackman AM, Darter JD, Wallace AS, Castel LD, Kalsbeek WD, Carey TS. The rising prevalence of chronic low back pain. *Archives of internal medicine*. 2009 Feb 9;169(3):251-8.
12. Hameed PS. Prevalence of work-related low back pain among the information technology professionals in India a cross-sectional study. *Int J Sci Technol Res*. 2013 Jul;2(7):80-5.
13. Chowdhury MO, Huda N, Alam MM, Hossain SI, Hossain S, Islam S, Khatun MR. Work-related risk factors and the prevalence of low back pain among low-income industrial workers in Bangladesh: results from a cross-sectional study. *Bulletin of Faculty of Physical Therapy*. 2023 Jun 7;28(1):20.
14. Momeni Z, Choobineh A, Razeghi M, Ghaem H, Azadian F, Daneshmandi H. WorkRelated musculoskeletal symptoms among agricultural workers: a cross-sectional study in Iran. *Journal of agromedicine*. 2020 Jul 2;25(3):339-48.
15. Sintayehu DW, Giziew A, Awrajaw D, Dawit G. Work-related risk factors and the prevalence of low back pain among low wage workers: results from a cross-sectional study. *BMC Public Health*. 2019;19(1072).

16. Wami SD, Abere G, Dessie A, Getachew D. Work-related risk factors and the prevalence of low back pain among low wage workers: results from a cross-sectional study. BMC Public Health. 2019 Dec;19(1):1-9.
17. Kim JY, Shin JS, Lim MS, Choi HG, Kim SK, Kang HT, Koh SB, Oh SS. Relationship between simultaneous exposure to ergonomic risk factors and work-related lower back pain: a cross-sectional study based on the fourth Korean working conditions survey. Annals of Occupational and Environmental Medicine. 2018 Dec;30:1-9.
18. Upadhyay D, Dinesh DK. A critical review of fundamental principles of Ayurveda.
19. Prasad S, Rao R, Ranjan R. Marma therapy in Katigraha WSR low back pain. Journal of Medical Science and Clinical Research, 5 (6). 2017:23070-4.
20. Madlur A, Joshi JR. Vata-The Niyanta and Praneta of Manas. Journal of Ayurveda and Integrated Medical Sciences. 2023 May 25;8(4):74-7.
21. Kumar T, Sanapeti RV, Prasad BS. Evaluation of the effect of poultice (Upanaha Sweda) in low back pain (Katigraha): A randomized comparative clinical trial. Ayu. 2019 Jul;40(3):159.
22. Gupta S, Patil V, Sharma R. Diagnosis and management of Katishoola (low back pain) in Ayurveda: A critical review. Ayushdhara. 2016;3:764-9.
23. Gupta S, Dey YN, Kannoja P, Halder AK, Sharma D, Wanjari MM, Chougule S, Pawar S, Kaushik A, Gaidhani SN, Gurav S. Analgesic and Anti-inflammatory Activities of Trayodashang Guggulu, an Ayurvedic Formulation. Phytomedicine Plus. 2022 Aug 1;2(3):100281.
24. Bhattacharya S. Sushruta—the very first anatomist of the world. Indian Journal of Surgery. 2022 Oct;84(5):901-4.
25. Jayasiri AP. Ayurveda Concepts of Joint Diseases. Rheumatoid Arthritis. 2022 Jan 19:187.

XXXX-XXXX

DOI :

Dr. Inter. J.Digno. and Research

This work is licensed under Creative

Commons Attribution 4.0 License

Submission Link : <http://www.ijdrindia.com>**Benefits of Publishing with us**

Fast peer review process

Global archiving of the articles

Unrestricted open online access

Author retains copyright

Unique DOI for all articles

<https://ijdrindia.com>